

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN HIGH SCHOOL 'X' JAKARTA

(Implementasi Pendidikan Inklusif Di Sma 'X' Jakarta)

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Abstract— Education is one of the facilities for mankind to develop itself, without exception for those who have limited or the specific needs. Hence inclusive education as a means of education to fulfill all children. Implementation inclusive education is done in several schools inclusive in various countries, including in Indonesia. In Indonesia has done the implementation inclusive, several education one of them is in Jakarta regional. Jakarta is the areas that is visible significant implement inclusive education. Based on the above explanation so this report is written to get a how implementation inclusive education high at the school level. Used descriptive research qualitative study. Then instrument used is interview various sources, observation of facilities school and learning process, and documentation. The data that has been obtained and analyzed and been validated by triangulation triangulasi source of data and. The research found the implementation of inclusive education in schools 'x' Jakarta. Schools 'x' Jakarta is not completely implement school inclusive education inclusive. This is because there are some requirements of school education providers that have not been inclusive, namely: schools did not using the curriculum entirely flexible and there are a few flaws in means and education infrastructure in accordance with standard operating procedure.

Keywords— *inclusive education; incusive school*

1. Introduction

Education is one of the facilities for mankind to develop itself. It is expressed in 1945 article constitution 28c verse (1) “everyone has the right develop itself through the fulfillment their basic needs, eligible to receive education and benefit from science and technology, art and culture, to improve the quality of his life and the sake of mankind”. Opening in 1945 the constitution it says that one of the objectives to the government of the republic Indonesia is the nation and every Indonesian citizen are entitled to fair and quality education in accordance with their interests and talent have regardless social status, ethnic and gender¹. If the truth, everyone receive are without except for those who require special needs caused by their disabilities.

In a book *Reform, Inclusion and Teacher Education*² talk about, In the 1948 declaration issued by the united nations human rights. In that declaration, discuss some things including on the right to education and full participation in society for everyone. In 1989, the UN convention on children rights to discuss the right of every child to get education. Then in 1990 in Jomtien Thailand held a conference of the world of education for all. Conference resulted in the main objective of, namely: bring all children enrolled and give all children to school appropriate. But in the implementation of, indeed still special needs children not getting an education (UNESCO 1992). Hence in the UN standard 1993 formulated regulations about the similarity opportunities for disabled people. In 1994 declaration Salamanca (UNESCO) signed by the education minister from several countries. The declaration of Salamanca emphasized that as he could, all the obviously learn together

regardless of difficulties or differences that there may be to them. Since then in April of 2000 in Dakar held the opening of the world education forum that make up the framework of the action of the world education. It is a result of the increasing focus the government several countries including the Indonesian government in developing Inclusive education.

On the face of it in Indonesia has reached pioneered inclusive education has changed since last year 1986 in a different form. At the time it had, a system of education which is valid for five named integrated education that was formally established through the decree of the minister on education and culture no.002 / u / 1986 government regulation no on administering integrated education in Indonesia. To early age education an integrated way, the son of disabled people could also happen due to attended public schools. But at the same time, they have to become acclimatized to driving a school system and made 'ready' to go to school in the public schools. And to know intelligent discernment 'ready' could I be sorry for, that the son of people with disabilities who want to attended public schools will have to follow all the applicable regulation in that school and nowhere and did not receive special treatment appropriate to their needs. If at finally the results provide some learned they cannot be searched, so considered to be problematic is the son of itself. While those whose school tuition was being carried by education inclusive on the other hand. Through education inclusive, school made to ready to accept all children with special needs. If in the end that the child does not study results in accordance, then who considered to be problematic is a system the implementation of inclusive education at the school³. Hence after education forum in the

world, Dakar the year 2000, the country have started to apply an inclusive education according to the results of the forum. According to the education forum in Dakar, an educational inclusive education that can satisfy all the needs of a child who normal as well as who require special needs.

The definition of inclusive education continues to grow, but has a big idea that the same, which is education for all children without exception for those who have flaws. Inclusive education is the education system is for the children who have special needs and special / or talent to receive education and in the same with students in general⁴. Based on the meaning of the inclusive education, can be seen that inclusive education it is very important to meet the needs of education for all children are of those with special needs. Hence the countries in the world that also continue to develop and implement an inclusive education. The Indonesian government implement an inclusive education in several regions. Jakarta, is one of cities in Indonesia are particularly noticeable evidently continued developing inclusive. Jakarta city administration start implement an inclusive education in schools since 2001. In 2001, there are 54 schools inclusive. According to the latest data Jakarta dept. of educational 2017 there are school inclusive 374, consisting of: 9 kindergarten, 261 primary school, 74 junior high school, 16 senior high school, and 15 vocational high school.

Apart from having too few maintains its inclusiveness school which has been growing. Jakarta government also makes its own regional regulations governing the implementation of inclusive education. The regulation of Jakarta no. 116 2007 years about the educational inclusive constitutes one of the references to the implementation of inclusive education to suit its purposes. Article 2 explained that the purpose of education is:

- improve understanding and respect for differences to toward the democratic;
- provide education according to human value;
- provided access to education as possible for all, specifically to receive a quality education.

To accomplish a purpose of education inclusive itself, the government coordination with several kindergarten /RA, primary school/MI primary school, junior high school/MT, vocational high school/MA public and private. Cooperation has to be done to the process of implementation of inclusive education. The inclusive education implemented in some chosen schools. Schools selected to implement inclusive education would have to fulfill some requirement. This requirement is:

- Has operational permission from the kabupaten government / city;
- can design and using the curriculum flexible;
- available educator and staff who have academic qualifications and competence in accordance with standard operating procedure;

- available of education facilities and infrastructure in accordance with standard operating procedure;
- available source of funding fixed guaranteed the realization of education and to students;
- recommendation the as school education providers inclusive from the kabupaten government / city and set as school education providers inclusive of administration. (requirements 6 number is closely related to facilities or support funds or facilities given by the government province and government in the education system inclusive).

Currently there are many schools inclusive that aims to make ends meet education all children including for those with special needs. But, in fact there is an inclusive school have not met those conditions. So schools inclusive cannot fulfill the needs of education for a wholly. There is still an inclusive school who is hostile to all the, there were even inclusive school which discriminate against children with special needs. Then there also the party that feel burdened with special needs student, because they did not understand how to give education services adapted to the special needs children⁵. And I thing that causes someone who is the pros and cons with inclusive education. Then based on data obtained from the directorate of special education training and specialized care (mudjito, in basic education harizal and elfindri, 2012) low child services with special needs also caused by a lack of teachers were willing and able to educate, crew members schools did not ready to give accessibility for education, crew members and his small operational budget provided by local governments to school.

Based on the above explanation and research is called: The implementation of education inclusive in high school X in Jakarta. It was done to get a how the implementation of education inclusive at the high school. If the school is not have been able to implement inclusive completely education, we must held an evaluation of the process of the education inclusive at the school. It was done that the school education provide implementation inclusive can reach its destination of education inclusive.

2. Methodology

A. Research Design

Type research used in this research was qualitative descriptive method. Descriptive is qualitative research methodology who describes and analyzes a phenomenon or the activity of going in the research⁶.

B. Research Subject

Study was conducted in one senior high school inclusive in Jakarta. The subject of study in this research using purposive sampling chosen. It was done researchers need for participants in accordance with characteristic to achieve research purposes in time as soon as possible⁷. The subject are the principal (deputed to vice principle of curriculum and inclusive education coordinator), vice principle of facilities, 3 subject teachers who

teaches in different levels and subject, 3 special needs student, 2 public students were at the different grade. Then to do, data validation researchers used data triangulation (interview, observation, and documentation), and source triangulation.

C. *Instrument and techniques of data collection*

Participants use the data from some instrument interview spring structure, the: observation, and documentation.

D. *Data Analysis*

As for our analysis the data used in this research was⁸:

- Noted the observation through interviews various sources, observation and documentation in the form of transkrip;
- Researchers conducted data coding, and data are distinguished and to direct and to waste;
- Validation the data that has been obtained by data triangulation (interview, observation and, and documentation) and source triangulation.
- Analyze the data give an interpretation on obtained by granting an qualitative. The data that has been grouped be explanation before one by researchers according to language;
- Withdrawal conclusion of research is, upon how implementation of inclusive education at the school.

3. **Result and Discussion**

Implementation is the application of idea, the concept, policy or innovation in an action practical⁹. While the implementation of inclusive education in schools means incorporating the concept of inclusive education inclusive one or education system into certain schools that impact.

According to the research in senior high school X in Jakarta is schools that have had operational permission from the district government/city. In addition in 2001, the school was chosen to be a school inclusive or school which implements inclusive education by the government of Jakarta. And there were a source of funds remaining that guarantees the continuity of the education system and not harming students. Things were due to according to interviews with, inclusive education coordinator he said that the source of operational funds schools the same with schools in general. Even if the schools it is receiving special needs student, there is no difference problems funds. That children who have special needs or no, they continue paying operational funds school such as schools in general. Then because the school is a school inclusive appointed by the government, so the school also received assistance funds for the implementation of education inclusive. These funds will help provide facility and infrastructure.

Equipment and infrastructure that was found on a unit of education providers inclusive education is a means and infrastructure that has been found in these schools and media plus accessibility as well as learning for learners of special

needs¹⁰. But in school x Jakarta equipment and infrastructure that supports the implementation of inclusive education especially facilities and infrastructure that supports the special needs students/still have some disadvantages. Because there is still deficient in, facilities and infrastructure then has special needs students received just children with autism, vision obstacles and hearing obstacles, etc.

Refer to the outcome of this research and the minister of national education republic of Indonesia number 70 years 2009 about for learners of inclusive education deficit disorder and have the potential to intelligence and / or talent special article 5 paragraph 1 and 2: (1) from special needs students and/or students have the potential to intelligence and/or special talent on a unit education consider the source of the power possessed school. (2) a unit of education as referred to in article 4 paragraph (1) allocate seats school tuition as referred to in article 3 paragraph (1) at least more than 1 school tuition in 1 (one) study groups that they will receive. It can be concluded that schools X Jakarta is having a clear picture of a school that is inclusive accept students with obstacles or potential based on ability to special schools or readiness to provide the education for all children.

Then there is a finding about students with special needs in school X Jakarta. This finding is all children with special needs in 2013-2014 are in the social class, among them no one was in science class. According to education coordinator inclusive and vice principle of curriculum, curriculum before the process of accepting new students with special needs the same with the process of new admissions in general, namely; through a test academic and non-academic. So that children with special needs received too have a good achievement at school the same as children generally. But 3 recent years, the government asks to school held education inclusive to give the special for special needs children, so that they can go to the without through a test like kids at generally. Therefore the quality, eager to study, and accomplishments special needs children now decreases. So that some teachers complain. They feel having difficulties in teach the special needs children having eager to study low, and it makes the learning process a little obstructed. Hence, to overcome these issues schools should be inclusive education providers have teachers and educational staff substandard academic qualifications and competence that will.

Standard academic qualifications and competence who deny the truth will: the capability of teachers to educate special needs children, and to educated special needs children a special kind of certain in the form of ¹⁰:

- Draw up an instrument assessments special education;
- carrying out assistance for special needs education;
- providing assistance a special service;
- provides guidance sustainable for a child with special needs;providing assistance to students who with special needs

Based on the research, although teachers and staff of standard academic qualifications. Still, sometimes teachers forgot to give special service for them or some teachers less patient to serve special needs children. This teaching because teachers classical with a number of children require special needs in class of highly little compared with students in general, the maximum students: 2 special needs children and 38 students. Common, aware for that reason there needs of teachers and increase staff.

Increase of teachers and staff, achieved through training and in the context of school, need adjustment in the context of school, need adjustment in school management, : from the point of view (values), personnel the school, and learning process¹¹.

Then this time, senior high schools X Jakarta has continued to increase the competency teachers and teaching staff works as follows:

- Understand law obvious, the state entitled to good quality education do not have to get school appointed, other schools and should hold. This special words mean intended to children with obstacles, troubled, their parents troubled, economic troubled, economic the be inclusive education services;
- coordinate with the government and colleges to endeavor socialize and increase understanding ability inclusive;
- invite speaker of higher education institutes which have the program is understanding the concept of inclusive education, as ui : , uhamka, uin;
- do training on asesmen, early detection, of advanced to all teachers and employees;
- conduct training about how special service either by speaker of mitranetra, pkkl, foundation tunarungu, santirama;
- a seminar on an inclusive education that are specially bring an education expert from inclusively; and
- working with parents to ensuring the success of inclusive education and equally understand. Hence public senior high schools X socialize the concept of inclusive education parents from common in every year for student / i and class x Parents.

Later as images more, above there is still one other inclusive school education providers. It is the curriculum used: The curriculum used in the school is curriculum flexibility adapted to the needs of each students include competency standard graduates and standard of competency standard base and competence.

Some characteristics that have not been completely was caused by a few things, namely: some facilities and infrastructure that were still are not yet available, one of them

is textbooks are written in braille for children with visual disabilities. The facility affects to the learning process for students who have obstacles. This is also mentioned by one of the teachers in a class x, he said that with the lack of textbook a lesson in braille. It is held up the learning process

Then to the problem of the absence of individual program of instruction and special programs to students have the potential to intelligence and talent special (pkbi). According to student affairs, it is difficult to carry out because the school is using the curriculum in accordance with the curriculum is obliged to used by regular school. Hence there is no special lesson plans for children with special needs at the school. In addition an inclusive education according to the coordinator, this school was regular school curriculum and things pertaining to the operation of all school following the rules of the education office. Hence there is no special lesson plans for children with special needs, existing only a special service appropriate to their need. Why not ? was said to be a drop in the ppi. Whereas according to mudjito, harizal, elfindri (2012) adapted the curriculum for education inclusive manner in which there is regular curriculum and individual program of instruction personnel. So schools is certainly still needed to provide this.

6. Conclusion

Based on exposure to above can be seen that if we see visions of the implementation of inclusive education through the terms of school education providers inclusive, then the school has not yet completely implement inclusive education. This is because they still have some conditions that have not been, namely: schools did not use flexible curriculum completely; there are a few flaws in means as well as education infrastructure that corresponds to standard operating procedure.

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